

CROACS: Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System

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As the barrier to entry for space operations decreases, and the commercialization of space increases, the rise in space debris is becoming a growing concern. Objects such as satellites, rocket stages, and fragmentation debris have become operational hazards when launching into orbit. The commonly used ground based satellite tracking systems do not have high enough resolutions to produce reliable estimates of an object's attitude, especially when the object is tumbling chaotically. Thus, the Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System (CROACS) will be responsible for determining and predicting the state of an uncooperative Client satellite's position and attitude dynamics (6 total degrees of freedom) to a higher degree of accuracy. The purpose of CROACS is to identify a Client satellite, characterize its current rotation, then simulate forward to predict the satellite's future states. This process starts with point cloud data from a LiDAR sensor being sent to our on-board processing unit. The Client is identified from the background and then, the on-board software determines the Client's position and attitude. Finally, the on-board software determines current angular velocities and predicts future states. CROACS is tested using a stand that rotates a scale model of a Client (1/82 scale Saturn V Second Stage) about three different axes. The outputs of the software are then validated using truth data that is captured within the Client model.

Nomenclature

ADR: Active Debris Removal

CONOPS: Concept of Operations

CROACS: Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System

DOF: Degree(s) of Freedom

FOV: Field of View

GEO: Geostationary Orbit

IMU: Inertial Measurement Unit

LEO: Low Earth Orbit

LIDAR: Light Detection & Ranging

TM: Template Matching

TOA²D²: Tumbling Object Acquire, Approach, Detumble, and Dock

TOF: Time of Flight

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I. Introduction

As orbits in space become more crowded with satellites, rocket boosters, and other objects, the issue of space debris is now a growing concern for future missions. Orbits like GEO and LEO serve critical functions for society, as they provide services such as communication, navigation, weather forecasting, surveillance, and more. As more companies and governments launch rockets and satellites into orbit, the chance of collisions on key satellites increases in likelihood. Decommissioned satellites and spent rocket boosters are some of the root causes of the congestion of debris in space[1]. To alleviate key orbits from potentially hazardous space debris, active debris removal (ADR) systems are needed. A crucial component of these ADR missions is in developing remote sensing techniques and software that can locate and characterize uncooperative objects. Shown below is a current proof of concept satellite created by this projects' company sponsor Astroscale [2].

Fig. 1 Astroscale ELSA-d Mission

Creating reliable ADR systems for uncooperative space debris is a difficult problem, with a variety of ongoing research looking into the subject [3]. Astroscale has proposed development on a new project called TOA²D²: Tumbling Object Acquire, Approach, Detumble, and Dock[4]. From this overarching mission, the scope for this project, chosen by the group, was to work towards designing, building, and testing a Close Range Orbital Attitude Characterization System (CROACS). This involves remotely sensing the object's dynamics, including its position, velocity, orientation, and angular velocity (a total of 6 degrees of freedom). As a whole, CROACS will serve as a proof of concept for the key link between approaching the tumbling body and physically interacting with it.

II. Design Objectives

A. Project Deliverables

The project undertaken by the group was to design, build, and test a system that can characterize and predict the current and future states of a tumbling object. Out of this goal, the primary deliverable desired by the company sponsor Astroscale was the software package used to do so, including the capability of scaling to more accurate (and expensive) LiDAR sensors.

B. Functional Requirements

The five high level functional requirements (FR) used to guide this project are outlined below in Table 1, and were used as a foundation for more detailed design requirements further in the design process.

FR 1	A sensor suite shall gather data from a scale model of an uncooperative, known space debris object.
FR 2	A software algorithm shall be created to analyze the Client's relative position, orientation, and angular velocity.
FR 3	An on-board computer shall be used for software processing.
FR 4	A test bench shall be built to hold the on-board computer and sensor suite.
FR 5	A Client object shall be created for algorithm testing and demonstration.

Table 1 Functional Requirements.

C. Concept of Operations.

Figure 2 below represents the CROACS concept of operations (CONOPS). This highlights the most important functions of the CROACS system and establishes the key nomenclature of the project, namely the Servicer and Client systems.

Fig. 2 CROACS Concept of Operations

D. Functional Block Diagram

The functional block diagram of the CROACS system can be seen below in Figure 3. This gives a high level overview of the system's operation as well as communication between subsystems.

Fig. 3 CROACS Functional Block Diagram

At the top of the diagram the user can be seen in blue. To activate the system, the user first powers on all the necessary components. Then the user inputs a rotation (tumble) command to the Client Host computer (The Potenta H7). That command is then broken out by Euler angles and rotation commands are distributed over WiFi to each motor's respective Arduino. While the Client body is rotating, encoders on each motor will collect rotation data, and secondary rotation data is collected by an inertial measurement unit (IMU). Also, while the Client is rotating the user shall initialize the Servicer subsystem. On board the Servicer is our LiDAR sensor and our on-board computer. The LiDAR will scan the Client and send point cloud depth data to the computer. Our determination algorithm will receive, process, and predict the attitude and position data of the Client in the form of quaternions and distance. The calculated data from the Servicer computer will be exported for a performance analysis. The Servicer data is sent to an external PC with timestamps via a hard wire or a flash memory stick. The Client truth data is recorded on the Portenta H7 and can be exported to the external PC in a similar fashion. Finally, with both sets of data manually synced based on the time stamps, an external analysis can be done of the algorithms accuracy and prediction performance.

E. Baseline Design

1. Client and Servicer

Figure 4 demonstrates the Servicer system, which is the combination of Servicer infrastructure and Servicer stand. The infrastructure of the Servicer includes the LiDAR sensor, its associated electronics, and the components required for on-board computing. This entire infrastructure is housed within a box at the top of the Servicer stand. The Servicer stand includes a post to elevate the LiDAR sensor to better isolate the Client, which will likely be sat on top of a table. The stand will also have the ability to be manually moved along two rails. This will allow for the simulation of small translational velocities often experienced by space systems during rendezvous/docking.

Fig. 4 Servicer System

Figure 5 demonstrates the Client system which is the combination of the Client model and three axes of motorized rotation. The Client model is a 1/82 scale Saturn V second stage and encloses onboard sensors that record truth data. Three motors are used to achieve the three axes of rotation. Motor 1 is mounted in a cluster that is inside the Client model and will rotate the model about its long axis. Motor 2 is mounted on the L arm and will rotate the model about its short axis. Finally, Motor 3 is held by the base stand and rotates the assembly of Motors 1 and 2 to achieve the third axis of rotation.

Fig. 5 Client System

2. Servicer Software

Fig. 6 Servicer Software Architecture

Figure 6 demonstrates the software structure for the Servicer system. The system begins by collecting raw LiDAR data of the rotating Client. The raw data is converted from depth and IR information into a point cloud. The point clouds are then sent to MATLAB for cleaning and processing.

After ensuring that they contain usable data, the point clouds are sent through the pre-processing module, containing noise reduction and background differentiation algorithm. These algorithms serve to get clean data similar to what would be seen in the space environment. In space, the LiDAR would only capture the Client, but for the purposes of our testing, we need to eliminate any points that are not a part of the Client (e.g., Removing the point clouds from the test bench/stand.).

Once the extraneous points are removed, the point clouds are sent to the main processing module, containing feature recognition and template matching. Template matching [5] serves as the primary algorithm for determining the Client's position, translational velocity, attitude, and angular velocity. The relative position solution is taken to be the centroid of the acquired point cloud. The algorithm then uses a database containing a point cloud of the Client in every possible orientation. It then compares the acquired point cloud to each template in the database, evaluating the correlation between the points within the two.

$$C(\Omega) = \frac{1}{N_P} \sum_{j=1}^{N_P} |\mathbf{P}_{Sensor}^{(j)} - \mathbf{P}_{Template}^{(j)}(\Omega)|^2 \quad (1)$$

As seen in Equation 1, the correlation C between the acquired point cloud, \mathbf{P}_{Sensor} , and a template point cloud, $\mathbf{P}_{Template}$, is taken to be the mean-squared distance of each j point for N_P total points in the point clouds. This is repeated for every orientation, Ω , in the database. The template associated with the lowest correlation value, or least mean-squared distance between points, is taken as the attitude solution. Both translational and angular velocity are acquired by the difference between the position and attitude estimates over a timestamp.

After acquiring the state vector information about the Client, the estimations are then sent to the post-processing module, which contains our prediction and error evaluation modules. Predicting the future Client states is conducted through statistical Euler angle characterization. This algorithm analyzes the estimations and determines the behavior of the data, such as sinusoidal or steady-state.

III. Design Methodology

To validate and improve upon the baseline design, a multitude of components, subsystems, and comprehensive tests have been formulated. These tests span all aspects of the project and will be conducted over the course of the spring semester. This section will provide details of a few key tests involving the Servicer subsystem, Client components, Client subsystem, and the entire system.

A. Servicer

1. Software Identification Testing

A critical aspect of this project is the system's ability to not only remotely sense the Client model, but to be able to distinguish unique features to allow for accurate template matching. To test our LiDAR's capabilities, the Client model will be held stationary and scanned at multiple distances and orientations. The stationary data will then be used as a preliminary validation of a large majority of the software, specifically noise reduction, background differentiation, feature recognition, and template matching.

Fig. 7 Software Identification Test Setup

The outcome of this test will provide us a better sense of how the LiDAR performs under a variety of different conditions such as lighting, distance, and colors on the model. This test will also reveal any range discrepancies and how to correct for them, making our software more accurate. This test is conducted prior to comprehensive testing, which involves full rotation, to allow team members to work in parallel with manufacturing and assembly.

B. Client

1. Motors and Controllers Testing

Testing of the motors and their controllers needs to demonstrate that the Arduinos (used to command motor direction and speed) can command motors above desired rate without physical interference problems, in order to verify electrical connections and power draw, and to validate that motors provide sufficient torque to rotate the Client body. The testing procedure involves 3 steps. First, assemble each motor and associated controller individually, meaning that Motors 1 and 2 with their respective Arduinos and Motor 3 (high voltage) using a compatible driver. Second, verify each spins at or above desired rate under load by physical measurement and stopwatch timing. Third, assemble overall Client setup by incrementally adding each motor, and testing rotations cumulatively.

C. Comprehensive Testing

Since, for the day in the life testing, multiple motors need to rotate at the same time while the encoders collect the data, comprehensive testing is necessary. This test validates that the Client can spin the rocket body simultaneously in 3 axes while transmitting encoder data. This procedure involves 3 steps. First, the motor 1 and 2 clusters will be assembled, which involves a servo, encoder and Arduino each. By this point, component testing is completed, so individual testing is not necessary. Second, motor 3 is assembled along with the power supply and driver. Third, code is run that will command motors to rotate the body at predetermined speeds and motions. After this, the encoder data is

recorded and then compared to that of the commanded rotations. This test will be successful if the recorded data is within 10% of the commanded data at all times.

1. *Vicon Verification*

In order to verify the encoder data and ensure the electronics and hardware of the Client are properly integrated, the Client system will be tested using the Vicon Sensing system located in the ASPEN lab at CU Boulder. The Vicon system is a motion tracking software that uses numerous infrared cameras placed about the perimeter of a testing area to record the position data of five to ten tracking dots, which are attached to an object that needs to be examined. The positioning of the cameras and an example of an object are shown in Figure 8 below. This system is commonly used to track human motion in the creation of video games or animated movies. Once the system is calibrated, and the Client is powered, various rotation scenarios will be performed with rotational position data being captured by both the Vicon software and encoders within the Client. These scenarios will only be recorded once the model has reached a steady state rotation so errors due to asynchronous time tags between the two recording systems can be mitigated. The outputs of this procedure will be rotational position data from both the encoders and the Vicon system. This data will be differentiated so the angular velocities from both data sets can be compared. The Vicon system has a very high resolution for its tracking (along the order of half a millimeter) and each of its numerous cameras report their respective error. Therefore, the data from the Vicon system will be treated as the truth. The result of this test will reveal any bias or error in the encoder data, which allows the team to rely solely on the encoder data during "Day in the Life" testing.

Fig. 8 Example of Vicon System

2. *Day in Life Testing*

The Day in Life testing needs to validate design requirements against original project goals and then validate Servicer software with Client model in various modes. The testing procedure is the following. First, the Servicer environment will be run so the LiDAR can begin data collection. Second, the Client will run through the desired rotation scenarios while data is being captured by the LiDAR and truth data systems. Then, the data between the Client and the state determination and prediction will be compared. Finally, this process will be repeated for other rotation scenarios with the possibility of variations like lighting conditions or translation of the Servicer stand.

IV. Design Results

A. Servicer System

As of writing this paper, the Servicer enclosure has been constructed, the on-board computer has been built, and preliminary LiDAR data acquisition has begun. Figure 9 demonstrates the initial results acquired from the software identification test described previously. Figure 10 shows the raw point cloud that was sent through the software modules and can be found in the Appendix.

(a) 3D printed Client body model

(b) Captured point cloud of Client model

Fig. 9 LiDAR Data for Client Model

The results from this test have revealed how the LiDAR behaves with respect to variables such as distance and colors on the Client model. As the Client distance increases with respect to the sensor, the point cloud of the model becomes more distorted in the scanning-direction. With this knowledge, we can restrict our scans to distances that minimize the distortion, allowing for more precise template matching. Darker colors on the Client are not picked up by the LiDAR as much as lighter colors are. For example, the black rim of Saturn V does not show up in the point cloud. We can use this to our advantage by using darker colors on the rotating stand attached to the Client. This will aid in the background differentiation module as only the Client will be contained in the point clouds.

Although the test has not been completed in its entirety, small changes are being made to the software structure and algorithms to prepare for subsystem and comprehensive testing in the coming weeks.

B. Client System

The Client system is currently in subsystem testing. As components of the Client are assembled (individual motor assemblies, electronic interfacing, etc.), they are tested to verify desired functionality in an effort to decrease issues that arise after assembly of the full system. Motors 1 and 2, the two servos, have been verified in their ability to rotate the model at the desired rate of at least 10 degrees per second. Motor 3, the stepper motor, has been powered and was able to smoothly rotate the L-arm that was machined from aluminum. Further testing is needed in order to determine the correct amount of micro-stepping that is required. In regards to the electronics of the Client, the initial plan of using Bluetooth to communicate between the Arduinos and Portenta failed during initial testing. While the Arduinos were supposed to communicate the position of the encoders, the test showed that no data was being transferred between the devices. To work around this, the communications of the Arduinos has been switched to WiFi. This only required software and network changes because the devices procured already had the hardware necessary to use a WiFi network. Using the same test, the new WiFi network has proven to communicate the data from the encoders. However, further testing and edits to the software are needed to optimize this system.

V. Conclusions

A. Future Work

Overall, the team is confident that we can meet all the design requirements and complete comprehensive testing before the end of the semester. For the overall field of space debris characterization, the team identified a few alternative strategies for future experiments and designs. With additional time and money, modifications to the design and implementation could have been made. Instead of constructing our own three-axis rotating stand, we could purchase one that comes with precise rotation measurements. Additionally, a higher-end LiDAR could be used to test at ranges more realistic to the space environment as well as capture data of higher resolution. This more expensive LiDAR would

have an easier time recognizing key features on the Client. The work being done with this project can be applied to other known objects besides a rocket booster. With additional algorithms in the software architecture, this project could be used on unknown objects, allowing for more space debris to be removed from orbit.

B. Lessons Learned

One major lesson learned was the importance of time management and planning. Due to a surge in COVID-19, the team was unable to meet in-person for the first two weeks of the spring semester. This impacted our manufacturing and testing schedule. In addition, lead times for certain components took significantly longer than expected. However, even with both of these roadblocks, we remain in good position to complete all of our testing, thanks in part to good margins on all testing dates and efficient work being conducted in parallel across subsystems.

Another key lesson learned was to have a plethora of backup plans. In the initial software implementation, we experienced a single point failure with our LiDAR sensor as it unexpectedly stopped working. This completely stalled all testing and progress as we had to troubleshoot the sensor while also formulating backup plans in case of complete failure. Fortunately, the error was found and fixed and the LiDAR became operational again. From this experience, we now have plans in case of failure for all single point failures.

Appendix

Fig. 10 Raw Point Cloud of Client Model

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